

Organizational Factors and Employee Productivity in Higher Education Institutions: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

This study examines organizational well-being in the education sector, with a focus on Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Although earlier research has explored aspects of organizational well-being, a comprehensive review linking well-being to both employee productivity and overall institutional performance is still lacking. To address this gap, the study conducts a bibliometric analysis of over 500 articles published between 2014 and 2025 using Biblioshiny. The analysis identifies emerging and underexplored themes related to workforce performance, welfare indicators, growth opportunities, and the mediating role of organizational factors. By presenting a systematic assessment of organizational well-being in HEIs, the study highlights the importance of leadership practices, professional development, and welfare initiatives—areas that remain insufficiently examined. The findings aim to guide future research and draw scholarly attention to evolving challenges and opportunities faced by academic staff in higher education.

Keywords: Higher Educational Institution, Bibliometrics analysis, Organisational Factors.

1. Introduction

Education includes all activities aimed at shaping, improving, and expanding human thought and behavior to help individuals reach higher levels of effectiveness in line with present and future goals. It equips people with information, skills, and attitudes that enhance personality, raise consciousness, and add value to society (Matheson, 2014). Bibliometric analysis further helps in understanding employee performance in higher education institutions by revealing research patterns and indicating areas where additional studies are required. This study seeks to identify emerging patterns in employee productivity within higher learning institutions, examine collaboration networks among authors, institutions, and countries, and highlight potential areas for future research on employee well-being and performance. It offers a fresh perspective by providing a structured analysis of organizational factors—such as leadership, occupational stress, work-life balance, training, and employee welfare—and their connection to productivity in Higher Educational Institutions. Unlike earlier qualitative studies based largely on subjective judgment, this research uses quantitative data supported by visualizations and network analysis. The study analyzes publication trends from 2014 to 2025 to clearly show how research on employee productivity in higher education has grown over the years and how different organizational factors influence performance. It also proposes relevant future research themes. Overall, the study delivers a comprehensive and systematic overview of theoretical foundations, common themes, and future directions in the field of employee productivity, helping to guide upcoming research in the higher education sector.

2. Review Methodology

2.1 Search procedure

Bibliometrics study generally makes use of the WOS and Scopus databases (Pranckute, 2021). In order to complete this investigation, the data that is considered to be of a higher quality was

extracted from the Web of Science record. The total number of articles obtained for the database was 96610 after the above-mentioned keywords were applied to all fields. Data download (savedrecs) occurred on August 1, 2025, according to the following search pattern. Early Access publications are not included. To address the research questions a systematic review of the literature was conducted. The English-language studies that were selected for this assessment of the literature examined the impact of occupational stress, work-life balance, leadership, training and development and employee welfare measures on the productivity of employees and elements of the organization in higher education institutions with publications dating from the years 2014 to 2025.

[‘Higher Education Institutions’ (title) OR ‘HEI’ (title) AND ‘India’ (title) AND ‘employees’ (title) OR ‘faculty’ (title) OR ‘academician’ (title) OR ‘facilitator’ (title) OR ‘lecturer’ (title) OR ‘educator’ (title) AND ‘leadership’ (title) AND ‘training and development’ (title) AND ‘employee well-being’ (title) AND ‘occupational stress’ (title) AND ‘work-life balance’ (title) OR ‘WLB’ (title) AND ‘employee welfare’ (title) AND ‘employee productivity’ (title) AND ‘employee performance’ (title) NOT ‘student (all field), (EXCLUDED- ‘early access’), (REFINED TO- ‘Open Access’), (REFINED TO - ‘Publication Years: 2014 - 2025’), (REFINED TO- ‘Articles, review articles, proceeding papers only’), (REFINED TO- ‘ Language: English’), (REFINED TO- ‘Management and Psychology Interdisciplinary’ in WOS Categories)]

2.2 Data collection

As mentioned earlier, WOS records were used in this study to get pertinent information. Only the years 2014 to 2025 are included in the data. For our analysis, we only include open-access publications; early access publications are not included. The language is refined to English exclusively for articles, review articles, and proceeding papers in document type (apart from book reviews, editorial material, and review articles). We selected the Management and Interdisciplinary Psychology in WOS categories, and then we proceeded with our analysis using the remaining 500 articles. The methodology used for this specific investigation is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Data Inclusion and Exclusion

S.No.	Filters	No. of articles
1-	Keywords ‘Higher Education Institutions’ OR ‘HEI’ AND ‘India’ AND ‘employees’ OR ‘faculty’ OR ‘academician’ OR ‘facilitator’ OR ‘lecturer’ OR ‘educator’ AND ‘leadership’ AND ‘training and development’ AND ‘employee well-being’ AND ‘occupational stress’ AND ‘work-life balance’ OR ‘WLB’ AND ‘employee welfare’ AND ‘employee productivity’ AND ‘employee performance’ NOT ‘student’	96810
2-	Excluded ‘early access articles’	94906
3-	Category ‘Open Access articles’	30063

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4-	Publication Year '2014 - 2025'	23455
5-	Document type - 'Articles, review article, proceeding papers'	19594
6-	Language- 'English'	19123
7-	WOS Categories- 'Management and Psychology Interdisciplinary'	400

(Source- Web of Science)

Performance analysis techniques, such as information on authors, documents, and productions as well as network analysis data and visualizations, were employed in this bibliometric analysis. Providing an up-to-date review of the many instruments available for conducting scientometric and bibliometric evaluations, such as performance evaluation tools, data gathering methods, and visualization approaches, is the goal of bibliometrics (Moral et al, 2020). It allows users to see bibliometric information, such as co-citation and co-word networks (Van Eck N, & Waltman L, 2009). We utilized the R program 'bibliometrix package' Biblioshiny and VOS viewer software to evaluate the data on staff productivity and organizational aspects in Higher Educational Institutions.

3. Results

The findings of the study objectives listed in the introduction are presented in this part. It contains all of the data pertaining to networks, countries, authors, sources, and popular subjects as well as different collaboration networks.

3.1 Sources information

The examination of the most pertinent sources, Bradford's Law, the number of articles overall and year-over-year growth trend, the local influence of the sources, etc. are all included in this section. The results of the data collection are indicated below (see Table 1). This indicates that the information was collected between 2014 to 2025. A total of 1088 writers and 103 sources, including article, review articles, and proceeding papers, comprised the 400 documents that were chosen for the study. The average number of citations per document is 21.77, and there are 1167 total keyword pluses (words that show up more than once in the titles of publications that are referred).

Table 1. Main information about the data

Description	Results
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2014:2025
Sources (Journals, Books etc.)	103
Documents	500
Annual Growth Rate %	8.09
Document Average Age	4.1
Average Citations per document	21.77
References	22797
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords plus (ID)	1167
Authors Keywords (DE)	1498
AUTHORS	
Authors	1088
Authors of single-authored document	41
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	42
Co-authors per document	2.97
International co-authorship %	38
DOCUMENT TYPES	
article	387
article; proceedings paper	2
review	11

(Source- Biblioshiny)

Table 2. Top Ten Relevant Sources

Sources	Articles
RESEARCH POLICY	39
JOURNAL OF TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER	24

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GENDER WORK AND ORGANIZATION	22
SCIENCE AND PUBLIC POLICY	20
JOURNAL OF NURSING MANAGEMENT	16
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION	11
PSICOLOGIA EDUCATIVA	11
MANAGEMENT LEARNING	10
INDUSTRIAL AND CORPORATE CHANGE	8
TECHNOVATION	8

(Source: Using Biblioshiny)

The top 10 publications with the most papers published during a certain period of time are listed in Table 2. The *Research Policy* Journal has published the most papers (n = 39), followed by the *Journal of Technology Transfer* (n = 24), *Gender Work and Organization* (n = 22), *Science and Public Policy* (n = 20), and so on. On this topic, the fewest articles (n=1) have been published by a no. of Journals including *Strategic Management Journal*.

Table 4 reveals the impact of the top ten local sources. It shows that “*Research Policy*” ranks first with an h-index of 18, followed by “*Gender Work And Organization*” with an h-index of 16. In terms of total citations, the journal “*Research Policy*” is leading (n=1324) whereas journal “*Gender Work And Organization*” is at second (n=842). Highest-cited articles have been published by both of these journals. “*Research Policy*” has the most articles published n=39, followed by the three journals- “*Journal of Technology Transfer*”, “*Gender, Work and Organization*”, “*Science and Public Policy*”.

Table 3. Leading Ten Source’s Local Impact

Element	h_index	TC	NP	PY_start
<i>Research Policy</i>	18	1324	39	2014
<i>Gender Work And Organization</i>	16	842	22	2019
<i>Journal of Technology Transfer</i>	14	656	24	2015
<i>Science And Public Policy</i>	9	282	20	2014
<i>Management Learning</i>	7	211	10	2014
<i>Academy Of Management Learning & Education</i>	6	132	6	2016
<i>British Journal Of Management</i>	6	522	6	2014
<i>Industrial And Corporate Change</i>	6	143	8	2015
<i>International Journal of Management Education</i>	6	151	11	2019
<i>Journal of Nursing Management</i>	6	125	16	2014

NP- Number of Publications, TC- Total Citations, PY- Publishing Year

(Source- Biblioshiny)

Figure 2. Bradford Law-based Evaluation of the Sources

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Samuel C. Bradford originally described Bradford's law in 1934. The entire amount of articles is split into three sections under Bradford Law, each of which includes one-third of all articles. 2 shows that Journals like “*Research Policy*”, “*Journal of Technology Transfer*”, “*Gender Work and Organization*”, “*Science and Public Policy*”, *Journal of Nursing Management*”, and “*International Journal of Management Education*”

fall under Zone 1 (known as Core Journals), Journals like *Psicologia Educativa*, *Management Learning*, *Industrial and Corporate Change* and *International Journal of Human Resource Management* fall under Zone 2 and Journals like *Human Resource Management Journal*, *Journal of Applied Behavioural Science and Management* and *Organization Review* fall under Zone 3 category journals (also known as Secondary Journals). Table 4 shows the most local cited sources. It reveals that “*Research Policy*” ranked as the top journal publishing 1838 articles, followed by “*Journal of Technology Transfer*” with 680 articles, then “*Academy of Management Learning*” with 356 articles etc. “*Strategic Management Journal*” is at the last position among top ten local cited sources list as it has published 225 documents only.

Table 4. Most Local Cited Sources

Sources	Articles
"Research Policy"	1838
"Journal of Technology Transfer"	680
"Academy of Management Learning"	356
Journal of Business Venturing	303
"Management Science"	283
"Organization Science"	279
"Technovation"	261
Academy of Management Review	257
"Small Business Economics"	246
"Strategic Management Journal"	225

Figure 3: Most Local Cited Sources

(Source: Biblioshiny)

3.2 Authors analysis

This section presents the most influential authors, their local impact, co-citation networks, leading affiliations, national scientific output, and the most cited countries. Table 6 lists the top 10 authors, with Lawson C. and Salter A. publishing the most papers (n=5), followed by Salandra R. and Seotanto D. (n=4). Lotka’s Law (1926), which explains the distribution of author productivity, is illustrated in Figure 5 and detailed in Table 7. It shows that 1029 authors produced only one paper, 56 authors produced two, 10 produced three, and only two authors produced four or five papers. Table 8 reports local author influence. Lawson C. and Salter A. lead with an h-index of 5, while Salandra R. follows with an h-index of 4. In total citations, Perkmann M. ranks highest, followed by Salandra R. The co-citation network (Figure 6) forms three clusters, led by authors such as Podsakoff PM, Vohora A, Clarysse B (Cluster 1); Dasgupta P, D’Este P, Cohen WM (Cluster 2); and Bercovitz J, Abreu M, Perkmann M (Cluster 3). The most productive affiliations (Table 9) show Lancaster University leading with 19 publications, ahead of Warwick (17) and Bath (15). Table 10 ranks the top publishing countries, with the UK (357), USA (216), and Italy (106) at the top; India does not appear in the top 10, indicating limited research activity in this

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area between 2014–2025. Table 11 lists the most cited countries, led by the UK (3108 citations), USA (852), and Italy (822), while Ireland ranks lowest with 198 citations.

Table 5. Top Ten Relevant Authors

Authors	Articles	Articles Fractionalized
Lawson C	5	1.75
Salter A	5	1.50
Salandra R	4	1.17
Soetanto D	4	1.33
Bristow A	3	0.92
Cai J	3	0.83
Hooi R	3	1.25
Lauring J	3	1.17
Mordi C	3	0.78
Perkmann M	3	0.92

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Figure 4. Authors' evaluation using Lotka's law

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Table 6. Analysis of Author's Productivity through Lotka's Law

Document written	No. of Authors	Propotion of Authors
1	1029	0.936
2	56	0.051
3	10	0.009
4	2	0.002
5	2	0.002

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Table 7. Top Ten Author's Local Impact

Element	h_index	TC	NP	PY_start
Lawson C	5	200	5	2015
Salter a	5	205	5	2014
Salandra R	4	267	4	2017
Bristow A	3	150	3	2017
Cai J	3	78	3	2020
Lauring J	3	56	3	2015
Perkmann M	3	342	3	2014
Rattle O	3	150	3	2017
Rizzo U	3	129	3	2015
Robinson S	3	150	3	2017

TC- Total Citations, NP- Number of Publications, PY- Publishing Year

(Source- Biblioshiny)

Figure 5. Authors' Co-Citation Networking

(Source- Biblioshiny)

Table- 8. Leading Ten Relevant Affiliations

Affiliation	Articles
UNIV LANCASTER	19
UNIV WARWICK	17
UNIV BATH	15
UNIV READING	15
KATHOLIEKE UNIV LEUVEN	13
RADBOUD UNIV NIJMEGEN	13
STELLENBOSCH UNIV	13
UNIV CAMBRIDGE	12
UNIV LEEDS	12
UNIV SURREY	12

(Source- Biblioshiny)

Table 9. Countries Scientific Production

Region	Frequency
UK	357
USA	216
Italy	106
Spain	99
Netherlands	97
Germany	78
Australia	49
China	47
Sweden	39
Belgium	36

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Table 10. Top Cited Nations

Country	TC	AAC
United Kingdom	3108	31.10
USA	852	18.10
Italy	822	30.40
Spain	762	23.10
Netherlands	545	18.80
Australia	360	30.00
Germany	279	15.50
Denmark	277	34.60
Norway	227	25.20

(Source- Biblioshiny)

3.3 Conceptual Structure

This section demonstrates the network approach, which incorporates factorial and thematic map analysis. A thematic map that shows the clusters found in the co-occurrence network from 2014 to 2025 which are based on Keywords Plus is shown in Figure 7. Based on a few criteria, the major themes have been split into four quadrants throughout the entire thematic map. First, the first quadrant displays motor concepts; second, advanced and isolated concepts; and third, leading or dipping notions. Fundamental, overlapping ideas or universal problems that cut across several academic disciplines are included in the fourth quadrant. Table 12 lists the terms in each of the four quadrants. Even if they have a high degree of relevance, the themes in Quadrant 4 are underdeveloped based on keyword plus. The relevant fields covered by quadrant 4 (leadership, higher education institutions, performance, motivation, etc.) may be the focus of future studies.

Figure 6. Thematic Map Analysis

(Source-Biblioshiny software)

Table 11. Thematic map Quadrant-wise Analysis

Quadrant 1	Quadrant 2	Quadrant 3	Quadrant 4
Identity	Academic fields	Societal impact	Business school
Career	Signaling Theory	Academic performance	Facilitation
Bibliometrics	Expertise	Unemployment	AI
Internationalization	Reflexivity	Academic publishing	Entrepreneurship education
Engagement	Qualitative		Innovation
Entrepreneurial Ecosystems	Organizational Culture		University-industry collaboration
Anxiety	Career Development		Diversity
Knowledge	SEM		Promotion and tenure
Stree	Academic staff		Gender
	Leader-member exchange		Higher education
			Leadership
			Faculty
			Performance
			Sustainability
			Motivation
			Academic engagement
			Framework
			Higher Education Institutions

Using the multiple correspondence analysis method, a word map is subjected to factorial analysis in Figure 8. Two clusters – one representing the pink-shaded area and the other the blue-shaded portion – as well as fifty terms were chosen overall, based on the authors' keywords. Cluster 2 (blue) is not formed here, while Cluster 1 contains the keywords faculty, impact, performance, leadership, knowledge, etc.

Figure 9 displays a word cloud generated using keywords plus. It is evident that the term "performance" is used more frequently (n = 74), then "knowledge" (n = 54), "impact" (n = 53), and so on. Figure 10 depicts academics, university, performance, higher education, gender, and so on as prominent words.

Figure 7. Word map under Factorial analysis

(Source-Biblioshiny)

Figure 8. Word Cloud

Terms	Frequency
performance	74
knowledge	54
impact	53
science	42
management	40
innovation	38
university	35
work	35
higher-education	29
model	28

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Figure 9. Density representation of Authors' keywords

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Table 12. Analysis of Countries' Collaboration

From	To	Frequency
United Kingdom	USA	21
United Kingdom	Italy	15
United Kingdom	Australia	12
United Kingdom	China	10
United Kingdom	Germany	10
United Kingdom	Netherlands	9
USA	Netherlands	8
United Kingdom	Spain	7
USA	Germany	7
United Kingdom	Belgium	6

(Source: Biblioshiny)

Figure 12. Collaboration Network of Institutions

(Source(s): Author's elaboration using Biblioshiny)

Figure 13. Three-Field Plot Analysis

(Source: Biblioshiny)

4. Discussion

This literature study had two main objectives. The first was to map the intellectual structure of the research domain by examining publication trends, contributing regions and countries, influential authors, relevant journals, research methods, keyword co-occurrence, and the most cited papers. The

second objective was to analyze how organizational factors influence employee performance in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Using content analysis, the study explored the roles of leadership, growth opportunities, welfare measures, and other organizational characteristics on employee outcomes. The results and future implications for higher education researchers are presented in the subsequent section.

Organizational factors strongly affect employee performance in HEIs. Job mobility often leads to temporary declines in performance (Lawson et al., 2015). Key organizational dimensions—such as work-life balance, occupational stress, leadership quality, training and development, and welfare measures—significantly shape employee productivity. Today's higher education administrators must manage institutional complexity, organizational culture, stakeholder expectations, and rapidly changing political, economic, technological, and social environments (Makoe & Olcott, 2021; Theodore & Montgomery, 2022). As work conditions evolve quickly, employees face modern challenges linked to time pressure and job instability.

Employees frequently experience stress due to unrealistic deadlines and supervisory pressure. Both married and single employees report similar stress related to role ambiguity and powerlessness. Unmarried academicians face added stress from role overload, conflict, and political pressure, often due to limited experience (Uniyal et al., 2019). HEIs also face pressure to produce highly competent faculty, which sometimes pushes individuals toward unethical practices (Raza et al., 2021; Williams & Dolan, 2020; Rahardja, 2019). Encouraging a focus on job resources and participation can help foster positive employee responses (Hakanen et al., 2006). Faculty often struggle to balance teaching with additional responsibilities, increasing strain and burnout (Bist et al., 2022).

Psychological capital moderates the relationship between performance and burnout, suggesting that recruitment should consider psychological strengths. Employees with higher psychological capital manage burnout more effectively. Training and development significantly enhance organizational performance (Gunu et al., 2013). Universities should expand training opportunities and encourage the optimal use of e-resources (Siwach et al., 2019). Professional development programs must align with key learning needs (Fadilla, 2020). Employee engagement is a strong indicator of job performance.

Welfare measures are essential, and their absence isolates employees within the organization (Rao et al., 2015). Organizations should prioritize welfare initiatives that enhance motivation and productivity. Conflict-management systems can help address gaps in organizational culture and employee attitudes. Training strengthens employee competencies, decision-making, teamwork, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills (Singh & Mohanty, 2012; Satterfield & Hughes, 2007). Resilient workers become stronger through learning and development (Janna et al., 2020). Strategic planning that supports employee needs—effective grievance handling, proper communication channels, and clear conduct guidelines—can transform organizational culture and improve employee performance.

5. CONCLUSION

Productivity serves as the catalyst for advancements in work performance, it is widely regarded as the essential component of organizational success. The study has examined a number of variables that affect employee productivity, including welfare programs, anxiety, career advancement and organizational culture. The study suggests the need for improved work-life balance options, including flexi time, job sharing, and breaks, to ensure employees feel a seamless coordination of family and professional lives. It also recommends reassessing policies and implementing social gatherings and public contact programs. Vision and constancy of purpose are the main responsibilities of leaders in school administration and planning. Encouraging faculty members to acquire fundamental teaching abilities, pedagogical methods, and classroom management strategies through organized training programs, mentorship opportunities, and teaching assistantships (Tiwari & Singh, 2024). Implementing frequent performance reviews and giving faculty members helpful criticism to assist them strengthen their areas of weakness and increase their effectiveness as teachers. Academic freedom and autonomy are cornerstones of higher education that influence the dynamics, practices, and culture of academic institutions. Future analysts are advised to look into this investigation using more comprehensive data in order to identify additional elements that affect the performance and provide a more reasonable

conclusion. Future studies could look into more free variables that affect how well employees execute their jobs and represent profitability.

6. Limitations and directions for future research

This review has certain limitations. It includes only articles published in the Web of Science database between 2014 and 2025, which may have excluded relevant studies; future research should incorporate additional databases. The study also did not use statistical tools to analyze quantitative relationships, and future work may adopt meta-analysis as suggested by Ceri-Booms et al. (2017). Research on factors affecting employee performance in higher education shows limited collaboration and quantitative output across countries, institutions, and scholars – including insufficient international collaboration with India – indicating scope for future partnerships. There is also a shortage of management literature on how organizational factors influence the productivity of employees in the education sector, highlighting the need for interdisciplinary research. To address these gaps, future studies should expand search parameters and databases. Thematic analysis also indicates underexplored topics such as career and engagement, organizational culture and leader-member exchange, societal impact, and leadership and sustainability. Only journal articles were included in this review; books, chapters, and early-access papers were excluded. Additional reliable sources may provide deeper insights. Overall, these findings offer a roadmap for future research on challenges faced by employees in higher education.

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